

Some results on Smarandache groupoids

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Abstract In this paper we prove some results towards classifying Smarandache groupoids which are in $Z^*(n)$ and not in $Z(n)$ when n is even and n is odd.

Keywords Groupoids, Smarandache groupoids.

§1. Introduction and preliminaries

In [3] and [4], W. B. Kandasamy defined new classes of Smarandache groupoids using Z_n . In this paper we prove some theorems for construction of Smarandache groupoids according as n is even or odd.

Definition 1.1. A non-empty set of elements G is said to form a groupoid if in G defined a binary operation called the product denoted by $*$ such that $a * b \in G, \forall a, b \in G$.

Definition 1.2. Let S be a non-empty set. S is said to be a semigroup if on S is defined a binary operation $*$ such that

- (i) for all $a, b \in S$ we have $a * b \in S$ (closure).
- (ii) for all $a, b, c \in S$ we have $a * (b * c) = (a * b) * c$ (associative law).

$(S, *)$ is a semi-group.

Definition 1.3. A Smarandache groupoid G is a groupoid which has a proper subset $S \subset G$ which is a semi-group under the operation of G .

Example 1.1. Let $(G, *)$ be a groupoid on the set of integer modulo 6, given by the following table.

*	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	0	5	0	5	0	5
1	1	3	1	3	1	3
2	2	4	2	4	2	4
3	3	1	3	1	3	1
4	4	2	4	2	4	2
5	5	0	5	0	5	0

Here, $\{0, 5\}, \{1, 3\}, \{2, 4\}$ are proper subsets of G which are semigroups under $*$.

Definition 1.4. Let $Z_n = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$, $n \geq 3$. For $a, b \in Z_n \setminus \{0\}$ define a binary operation $*$ on Z_n as: $a * b = ta + ub \pmod{n}$ where t, u are 2 distinct elements in $Z_n \setminus \{0\}$ and $(t, u) = 1$. Here “+” is the usual addition of two integers and “ ta ” mean the product of the two integers t and a .

Elements of Z_n form a groupoid with respect to the binary operation. We denote these groupoids by $\{Z_n(t, u), *\}$ or $Z_n(t, u)$ for fixed integer n and varying $t, u \in Z_n \setminus \{0\}$ such that $(t, u) = 1$. Thus we define a collection of groupoids $Z(n)$ as follows

$$Z(n) = \{Z_n(t, u), * \mid \text{for integers } t, u \in Z_n \setminus \{0\} \text{ such that } (t, u) = 1\}.$$

Definition 1.5. Let $Z_n = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$, $n \geq 3$. For $a, b \in Z_n \setminus \{0\}$, define a binary operation $*$ on Z_n as: $a * b = ta + ub \pmod{n}$ where t, u are two distinct elements in $Z_n \setminus \{0\}$ and t and u need not always be relatively prime but $t \neq u$. Here “+” is usual addition of two integers and “ ta ” means the product of two integers t and a .

For fixed integer n and varying $t, u \in Z_n \setminus \{0\}$ s.t $t \neq u$ we get a collection of groupoids $Z^*(n)$ as: $Z^*(n) = \{Z_n(t, u), * \mid \text{for integers } t, u \in Z_n \setminus \{0\} \text{ such that } t \neq u\}$.

Remarks 1.1. (i) Clearly, $Z(n) \subset Z^*(n)$.

(ii) $Z^*(n) \setminus Z(n) = \Phi$ for $n = p + 1$ for prime $p = 2, 3$.

(iii) $Z^*(n) \setminus Z(n) \neq \Phi$ for $n \neq p + 1$ for prime p .

We are interested in Smarandache Groupoids which are in $Z^*(n)$ and not in $Z(n)$ i.e., $Z^*(n) \setminus Z(n)$.

§2. Smarandache groupoids when n is even

Theorem 2.1. Let $Z_n(t, lt) \in Z^*(n) \setminus Z(n)$. If n is even, $n > 4$ and for each $t = 2, 3, \dots, \frac{n}{2} - 1$ and $l = 2, 3, 4, \dots$ such that $lt < n$, then $Z_n(t, lt)$ is Smarandache groupoid.

Proof. Let $x = \frac{n}{2}$.

Case 1. t is even.

$$x * x = xt + ltx = (l + 1)tx \equiv 0 \pmod{n}.$$

$$x * 0 = xt \equiv 0 \pmod{n}.$$

$$0 * x = lxt \equiv 0 \pmod{n}.$$

$$0 * 0 = 0 \pmod{n}.$$

$\therefore \{0, x\}$ is semigroup in $Z_n(t, lt)$.

$\therefore Z_n(t, lt)$ is Smarandache groupoid when t is even.

Case 2. t is odd.

(a) If l is even.

$$x * x = xt + ltx = (l + 1)tx \equiv x \pmod{n}.$$

$\{x\}$ is semigroup in $Z_n(t, lt)$.

$\therefore Z_n(t, lt)$ is Smarandache groupoid when t is odd and l is even.

(b) If l is odd then $(l + 1)$ is even.

$$x * x = xt + ltx = (l + 1)tx \equiv 0 \pmod{n}.$$

$$x * 0 = xt \equiv x \pmod{n}.$$

$$0 * x = ltx \equiv x \pmod{n}.$$

$$0 * 0 \equiv 0 \pmod{n}.$$

$$\Rightarrow \{0, x\} \text{ is semigroup in } Z_n(t, lt).$$

$\therefore Z_n(t, lt)$ is Smarandache groupoid when t is odd and l is odd.

Theorem 2.2. Let $Z_n(t, u) \in Z^*(n) \setminus Z(n)$, n is even $n > 4$ where $(t, u) = r$ and $r \neq t, u$ then $Z_n(t, u)$ is Smarandache groupoid.

Proof. Let $x = \frac{n}{2}$.

Case 1. Let r be even i.e t and u are even.

$$x * x = tx + ux = (t + u)x \equiv 0 \pmod{n}.$$

$$0 * x = ux \equiv 0 \pmod{n}.$$

$$x * 0 = tx \equiv 0 \pmod{n}.$$

$$0 * 0 = 0 \pmod{n}.$$

$$\{0, x\} \text{ is semigroup in } Z_n(t, lt).$$

$\therefore Z_n(t, lt)$ is Smarandache groupoid when t is even and u is even.

Case 2. Let r be odd.

(a) when t is odd and u is odd,

$$\Rightarrow t + u \text{ is even.}$$

$$x * x = tx + ux = (t + u)x \equiv 0 \pmod{n}.$$

$$x * 0 = tx \equiv x \pmod{n}.$$

$$0 * x \equiv ux \equiv x \pmod{n}.$$

$$0 * 0 \equiv 0 \pmod{n}.$$

$$\{0, x\} \text{ is a semigroup in } Z_n(t, u).$$

$\therefore Z_n(t, u)$ is Smarandache groupoid when t is odd and u is odd.

(b) when t is odd and u is even,

$$\Rightarrow t + u \text{ is odd.}$$

$$x * x = tx + ux = (t + u)x \equiv x \pmod{n}.$$

$$\{x\} \text{ is a semigroup in } Z_n(t, u).$$

$\therefore Z_n(t, u)$ is Smarandache groupoid when t is odd and u is even.

(c) when t is even and u is odd,

$$\Rightarrow t + u \text{ is odd.}$$

$$x * x = tx + ux = (t + u)x \equiv x \pmod{n}.$$

$$\{x\} \text{ is a semigroup in } Z_n(t, u).$$

$\therefore Z_n(t, u)$ is Smarandache groupoid when t is even and u is odd.

By the above two theorems we can determine Smarandache groupoids in $Z^*(n) \setminus Z(n)$ when n is even and $n > 4$.

We find Smarandache groupoids in $Z^*(n) \setminus Z(n)$ for $n = 22$ by Theorem 2.1.

t	l	$lt < 22$	$Z_n(t, lt)$	Proper subset which is semigroup	Smarandache groupoid in $Z^*(n) \setminus Z(n)$
2	2	4	$Z_{22}(2, 4)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(2, 4)$
	3	6	$Z_{22}(2, 6)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(2, 6)$
	4	8	$Z_{22}(2, 8)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(2, 8)$
	5	10	$Z_{22}(2, 10)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(2, 10)$
	6	12	$Z_{22}(2, 12)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(2, 12)$
	7	14	$Z_{22}(2, 14)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(2, 14)$
	8	16	$Z_{22}(2, 16)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(2, 16)$
	9	18	$Z_{22}(2, 18)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(2, 18)$
	10	20	$Z_{22}(2, 20)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(2, 20)$
3	2	6	$Z_{22}(3, 6)$	$\{11\}$	$Z_{22}(3, 6)$
	3	9	$Z_{22}(3, 9)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(3, 9)$
	4	12	$Z_{22}(3, 12)$	$\{11\}$	$Z_{22}(3, 12)$
	5	15	$Z_{22}(3, 15)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(3, 15)$
	6	18	$Z_{22}(3, 18)$	$\{11\}$	$Z_{22}(3, 18)$
	7	21	$Z_{22}(3, 21)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(3, 21)$
4	2	8	$Z_{22}(4, 8)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(4, 8)$
	3	12	$Z_{22}(4, 12)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(4, 12)$
	4	16	$Z_{22}(4, 16)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(4, 16)$
	5	20	$Z_{22}(4, 20)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(4, 20)$
5	2	10	$Z_{22}(5, 10)$	$\{11\}$	$Z_{22}(5, 10)$
	3	15	$Z_{22}(5, 15)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(5, 15)$
	4	20	$Z_{22}(5, 20)$	$\{11\}$	$Z_{22}(5, 20)$
6	2	12	$Z_{22}(6, 12)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(6, 12)$
	3	18	$Z_{22}(6, 18)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(6, 18)$
7	2	14	$Z_{22}(7, 14)$	$\{11\}$	$Z_{22}(7, 14)$
	3	21	$Z_{22}(7, 21)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(7, 21)$
8	2	16	$Z_{22}(8, 16)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(8, 16)$
9	2	18	$Z_{22}(9, 18)$	$\{11\}$	$Z_{22}(9, 18)$
10	2	20	$Z_{22}(10, 20)$	$\{0, 11\}$	$Z_{22}(10, 20)$

Next, we find Smarandache groupoids in $Z^*(n) \setminus Z(n)$ for $n = 22$ by Theorem 2.2.

t	u	(t, u) = r r ≠ t, u	Z₂₂(t, u)	Proper subset which is semigroup	Smarandache groupoid in Z*(n) \ Z(n)
4	6	(4,6)=2	Z ₂₂ (4, 6)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (4, 6)
	10	(4,10)=2	Z ₂₂ (4, 10)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (4, 10)
	14	(4,14)=2	Z ₂₂ (4, 14)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (4, 14)
	18	(4,18)=2	Z ₂₂ (4, 18)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (4, 18)
6	8	(6,8)=2	Z ₂₂ (6, 8)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (6, 8)
	9	(6,9)=3	Z ₂₂ (6, 9)	{11}	Z ₂₂ (6, 9)
	10	(6,10)=2	Z ₂₂ (6, 10)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (6, 10)
	14	(6,14)=2	Z ₂₂ (6, 14)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (6, 14)
	16	(6,16)=2	Z ₂₂ (6, 16)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (6, 16)
	20	(6,20)=2	Z ₂₂ (6, 20)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (6, 20)
	21	(6,21)=3	Z ₂₂ (6, 21)	{11}	Z ₂₂ (6, 21)
8	10	(8,10)=2	Z ₂₂ (8, 10)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (8, 10)
	12	(8,12)=4	Z ₂₂ (8, 12)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (8, 12)
	14	(8,14)=2	Z ₂₂ (8, 14)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (8, 14)
	18	(8,18)=2	Z ₂₂ (8, 18)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (8, 18)
	20	(8,20)=4	Z ₂₂ (8, 20)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (8, 20)
9	21	(9,21)=3	Z ₂₂ (9, 21)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (9, 21)
10	12	(10,12)=2	Z ₂₂ (10, 12)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (10, 12)
	14	(10,14)=2	Z ₂₂ (10, 14)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (10, 14)
	16	(10,16)=2	Z ₂₂ (10, 16)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (10, 16)
	18	(10,18)=2	Z ₂₂ (10, 18)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (10, 19)
12	14	(12,14)=2	Z ₂₂ (12, 14)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (12, 14)
	15	(12,15)=3	Z ₂₂ (12, 15)	{11}	Z ₂₂ (12, 15)
	16	(12,16)=4	Z ₂₂ (12, 16)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (12, 16)
	18	(12,18)=6	Z ₂₂ (12, 18)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (12, 18)
	20	(12,20)=4	Z ₂₂ (12, 20)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (12, 20)
	21	(12,21)=3	Z ₂₂ (12, 21)	{11}	Z ₂₂ (12, 21)
14	16	(14,16)=2	Z ₂₂ (14, 16)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (14, 16)
	18	(14,18)=2	Z ₂₂ (14, 18)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (14, 18)
	20	(14,20)=2	Z ₂₂ (14, 20)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (14, 20)
	21	(14,21)=7	Z ₂₂ (14, 21)	{11}	Z ₂₂ (14, 21)
15	20	(15,20)=5	Z ₂₂ (15, 20)	{11}	Z ₂₂ (15, 20)
16	18	(16,18)=2	Z ₂₂ (16, 18)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (16, 18)
	20	(16,20)=4	Z ₂₂ (16, 20)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (16, 20)
18	20	(18,20)=2	Z ₂₂ (18, 20)	{0, 11}	Z ₂₂ (18, 20)

§3. Smarandache groupoids when n is odd

Theorem 3.1. Let $Z_n(t, u) \in Z^*(n) \setminus Z(n)$. If n is odd, $n > 4$ and for each $t = 2, \dots, \frac{n-1}{2}$, and $u = n - (t - 1)$ such that $(t, u) = r$ then $Z_n(t, u)$ is Smarandache groupoid.

Proof. Let $x \in \{0, \dots, n - 1\}$.

$$x * x = xt + xu = (n + 1)x \equiv x \pmod{n}.$$

$\therefore \{x\}$ is semigroup in Z_n .

$\therefore Z_n(t, u)$ is Smarandache groupoid.

By the above theorem we can determine the Smarandache groupoids in $Z^*(n) \setminus Z(n)$ when n is odd and $n > 4$.

Also we note that all $\{x\}$ where $x \in \{0, \dots, n - 1\}$ are proper subsets which are semigroups in $Z_n(t, u)$.

Let us consider the examples when n is odd. We will find the Smarandache groupoids in $Z^*(n) \setminus Z(n)$ by Theorem 3.1.

n	t	$u = n - (t - 1)$	$(t, u) = r$	$Z_n(t, u)$ Smarandache groupoid (S.G.) in $Z^*(n) \setminus Z(n)$
5	2	4	$(2, 4) = 2$	$Z_5(2, 4)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(5) \setminus Z(5)$
7	2	6	$(2, 6) = 3$	$Z_7(2, 6)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(7) \setminus Z(7)$
9	2	8	$(2, 8) = 2$	$Z_9(2, 8)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(9) \setminus Z(9)$
	4	6	$(4, 6) = 2$	$Z_9(4, 6)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(9) \setminus Z(9)$
11	2	10	$(2, 10) = 2$	$Z_{11}(2, 10)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(11) \setminus Z(11)$
	3	9	$(3, 9) = 3$	$Z_{11}(3, 9)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(11) \setminus Z(11)$
	4	8	$(4, 8) = 4$	$Z_{11}(4, 8)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(11) \setminus Z(11)$
13	2	12	$(2, 12) = 2$	$Z_{13}(2, 12)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(13) \setminus Z(13)$
	4	10	$(4, 10) = 2$	$Z_{13}(4, 10)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(13) \setminus Z(13)$
	6	8	$(6, 8) = 2$	$Z_{13}(6, 8)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(13) \setminus Z(13)$
15	2	14	$(2, 14) = 2$	$Z_{15}(2, 14)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(15) \setminus Z(15)$
	4	12	$(4, 12) = 4$	$Z_{15}(4, 12)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(15) \setminus Z(15)$
	6	10	$(6, 10) = 2$	$Z_{15}(6, 10)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(15) \setminus Z(15)$
17	2	16	$(2, 16) = 2$	$Z_{17}(2, 16)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(17) \setminus Z(17)$
	3	15	$(3, 15) = 3$	$Z_{17}(3, 15)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(17) \setminus Z(17)$
	4	14	$(4, 14) = 2$	$Z_{17}(4, 14)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(17) \setminus Z(17)$
	6	12	$(6, 12) = 6$	$Z_{17}(6, 12)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(17) \setminus Z(17)$
	8	10	$(8, 10) = 2$	$Z_{17}(8, 10)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(17) \setminus Z(17)$

n	t	$u = n - (t - 1)$	$(t, u) = r$	$Z_n(t, u)$ Smarandache groupoid (S.G.) in $Z^*(n) \setminus Z(n)$
19	2	18	$(2, 18) = 2$	$Z_{19}(2, 18)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(19) \setminus Z(19)$
	4	16	$(4, 16) = 4$	$Z_{19}(4, 16)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(19) \setminus Z(19)$
	5	15	$(5, 15) = 5$	$Z_{19}(5, 15)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(19) \setminus Z(19)$
	6	14	$(6, 14) = 2$	$Z_{19}(6, 14)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(19) \setminus Z(19)$
	8	12	$(8, 12) = 4$	$Z_{19}(8, 12)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(19) \setminus Z(19)$
21	2	20	$(2, 20) = 2$	$Z_{21}(2, 20)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(21) \setminus Z(21)$
	4	18	$(4, 18) = 2$	$Z_{21}(4, 18)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(21) \setminus Z(21)$
	6	16	$(6, 16) = 2$	$Z_{21}(6, 16)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(21) \setminus Z(21)$
	8	14	$(8, 14) = 2$	$Z_{21}(8, 14)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(21) \setminus Z(21)$
	10	12	$(10, 12) = 2$	$Z_{21}(10, 12)$ is S.G. in $Z^*(21) \setminus Z(21)$

Open Problems:

1. Let n be a composite number. Are all groupoids in $Z^*(n) \setminus Z(n)$ Smarandache groupoids?
2. Which class will have more number of Smarandache groupoids in $Z^*(n) \setminus Z(n)$?
 - (a) When $n + 1$ is prime.
 - (b) When n is prime.

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